

Free Energy Changes vis-a-vis other Thermodynamical Parameters as a Measure of Stability—A Solid Phase Study of Heats of Formation and Lattice Energies of β - and γ -Picoline Complexes of Fluoborates of some Transitional Metals : Part II

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In a comparatively thorough investigation with a series of compounds of α , β and γ -picoline complexes of the fluoborates of Co, Ni, Zn and Cd, an attempt has been made to see which one amongst the thermodynamic parameters namely ΔH , ΔS , ΔF , Lattice energy and heats of formation, is more reliable, useful and recommendable for a study of the stability of comparable complexes. This publication deals with the limitations of the values of lattice energy and heats of formation.

Having observed that the heat of dissociation (ΔH) is not a suitable measure of stability of the picoline complexes¹ of fluoborates, attempts have been made to evaluate their heats of formation and Lattice energies in order to find if these could be correlated with their stability. To measure the order of stability it has been the practice² to determine the heat of formation calorimetrically by the application of Hess's Law of Heat Summation.

In a solid phase study, the determination of Lattice energies appears to be equally significant.

Determination of Heat of Formation : The heat of formation of a complex was determined by the following general thermochemical equations :

$$\therefore M(\text{BF}_4)_2 + 4(\text{Pico}) = M(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{Pico} + q_1 + q + q_3 - q' + 4q_2$$

Except q and q' , the rest of the thermal data could be experimentally determined. Since the hydrated fluoborates decomposed on heating the anhydrous compounds could not be prepared, q was therefore indirectly determined on the basis of the following considerations : The heat of solution of anhydrous salt, $L = q + L'$, (L' heat solution of hydrated salt). The

1. *This Journal*, previous publication, 1969.

2. H. Heiber, *Z. anorg. u. allgem. chem.*, 1930, **186**, 97; *Z. anorg. chem.*, 1931, **196**, 193.

heat of solution L of anhydrous fluoborate was evaluated from Fajan's equation: $L = W_h^+ - W_h^- - U_1$, wherein $U_1 =$ Lattice energy of the salt, W_h^+ and W_h^- are the heats of hydration of cation and anion respectively. The values of L and L' are shown in Table I. L was calculated from the data on W_h^+ , W_h^- and U_1 , given by Kapustiniskii and Yatsimirskii^{3,4} and L' was experimentally determined.

The value of q' was taken from that given by Thomsen⁵.

TABLE I

Compounds	U_1 K.cal.	W_h^+ K.cal.	W_h^- K.cal.	L K.cal.	L' K.cal.	q K.cal.
Co(BF ₄) ₂	508.3	435.5	64.0	55.2	1.40	53.79
Ni(BF ₄) ₂	510.5	444.3	64.0	61.8	2.31	59.48
Zn(BF ₄) ₂	493.0	406.0	64.0	41.0	1.043	39.95
Cd(BF ₄) ₂	463.0	361.7	64.0	26.7	0.515	26.185

TABLE II

Compounds	Heat of reaction G.F.W. K.cal (Mean value) in H ₂ SO ₄			Heat of formation (Q) in K.cal G.F.W.
	(q ₁)	(q ₂)	(q ₃)	
Co(BF ₄) ₂ 4β-pico	—	—	17.86	62.46
Ni(BF ₄) ₂ 4β-pico	—	—	11.76	72.25
Zn(BF ₄) ₂ 4β-pico	—	—	21.27	43.22
Cd(BF ₄) ₂ 4β-pico	—	—	4.29	45.71
Co(BF ₄) ₂ 4γ-pico	—	—	17.86	65.52
Ni(BF ₄) ₂ 4γ-pico	—	—	32.72	54.35
Zn(BF ₄) ₂ 4γ-pico	—	—	15.73	51.82
Cd(BF ₄) ₂ 4γ-pico	—	—	4.55	48.51
Co(BF ₄) ₂ .6H ₂ O	1.434	—	—	—
Ni(BF ₄) ₂ .6H ₂ O	1.4352	—	—	—
Zn(BF ₄) ₂ .6H ₂ O	1.4352	—	—	—
Cd(BF ₄) ₂ .6H ₂ O	0.7214	—	—	—
β-Picoline	—	9.77	—	—
γ-Picoline	—	10.04	—	—

By putting the values of q_1 , q_2 and q_3 , q and q' in the above thermochemical equation, the heat of formation (Q) for the respective complexes could be determined.

3. A. F. Kapustiniskii, *Quarterly Review*, 1956, **10**, 283.
4. K. B. Yatsimirskii, *J. Gen. Chem. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1947, **17**, 2019.
5. J. W. Mellor's. A comprehensive treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry, Vol. 10, p. 405, Ed. 1952, Longmans Green, London.

Calculation of Lattice energy : Of the available equations⁶ for the calculation of Lattice energy that of Kapustiniskii was found expedient. According to this equation

$$U_2 = 287.2 \Sigma n \frac{m_c + m_a}{r_c + r_a} \left[1 - \frac{0.345}{r_c + r_a} + 0.00453(r_c + r_a) \right] \text{K.cal.}$$

where Σn = Total number of ions in the molecule. m_c , m_a , r_c and r_a are valencies and radii of the cation and anion respectively. r_c of a complex cation is calculated with the help of the equation of Yatsimirskii

$$= \frac{11.65}{I^{1/3}}$$

where I = Ionic concentration = $\frac{1000\nu n}{M}$

$$\nu = d$$

n = Number of molecules co-ordinated.

M = Molecular Wt. of complex ion.

In a second attempt, use is made of a thermochemical cycle⁷.

The expression : $U_2 = U_1 + Q - E$.

where U_2 = Lattice energy of complex salt.

U_1 = Lattice energy of simple salt.

Q = Heat of formation of the complex salt.

E = Co-ordination Energy.

U_1 evaluated from Kapustiniskii's equation, Q is experimentally determined as shown in Table II. E is theoretically calculated from an equation of K. B. Yatsimirskii.

$$E = \frac{Ne^2m^2(1-1/D)}{r_c + \beta r^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

N = Avogadro's number

e = Charge of the electron

m = Charge of the ion

r_c = Radius of the complex cation

$\beta r^{\frac{1}{2}}$ = Distance between the ion and the nearest pole of ligand dipole (= 0.73 approx.)

D = Dielectric constant of the medium.

The term D could be determined from Jeffries Wyman's equation⁹

$$P = \frac{D+1}{8.5}$$

6. Progress in Solid State Chemistry, Vol. I, Edited by H. Reiss, Paragon Press, London, 1964.

7. W. Biltz and H. G. Grim, *Z. anorg. allgem. chem.*, 1925, **145**, 63.

8. K. B. Yatsimirskii, (*loc. cit.*).

9. Jeffries Wyman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1482.

P = Ideal polarization per c.c. The ideal polarization per c.c. and β and γ -picoline was calculated from their values of total molar polarization and molar volumes, as found in the literature. The total molar polarization of β and γ -picolines had been determined as 146.99 and 167.88 respectively by C. W. Cumper, A. I. Vogel and S. Wacker¹⁰. The compound molar volumes came to 96.87 c.c. and 97.26 c.c. respectively. So the values P for β and γ -picoline came to 1.517 and 1.726 per c.c. respectively. Accordingly, the above equation gave the D values as 11.8979 and 13.6710 for β and γ -picoline respectively. The values of E of all the complex cation under investigation were evaluated. Consequently, by knowing the values U_1 , Q and E , it was possible to find out the Lattice energy U_2 of the complexes from thermochemical points of view. This expression involves the term Q , which has to be determined experimentally. So, the evaluation of U_2 from thermochemical cycle is partly experimental and partly theoretical. The values thus found from Kapustiniskii's equation and from thermochemical cycle consideration are tabulated below :—

TABLE III

Lattice Energies of the Complexes

Compounds	U_2 K.cal/mole Kapustiniskii	U_2 K.cal/mole Thermochemical cycle
Co(BF ₄) ₂	4 β -pico	250.4
	3 β -pico	247.7
	2 β -pico	245.4
Ni(BF ₄) ₂	4 β -pico	249.9
	3 β -pico	247.3
	2 β -pico	242.9
Zn(BF ₄) ₂	4 β -pico	248.8
	3 β -pico	247.3
	2 β -pico	242.4
Cd(BF ₄) ₂	4 β -pico	248.9
	3 β -pico	248.0
	2 β -pico	238.2
Co(BF ₄) ₂	4 γ -pico	250.4
	3 γ -pico	247.7
	2 γ -pico	245.4
Ni(BF ₄) ₂	4 γ -pico	249.9
	3 γ -pico	247.3
	2 γ -pico	242.9
Zn(BF ₄) ₂	4 γ -pico	248.8
	3 γ -pico	247.3
	2 γ -pico	242.4
Cd(BF ₄) ₂	4 γ -pico	248.9
	3 γ -pico	248.0
	2 γ -pico	238.2

10. C. W. Cumper *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 3621.

DISCUSSION

The application of Lattice energy to assess the stability order of the comparable complexes may not be helpful as it is evident from Table III that the two approaches differ by 12 to 50 Kcals./mole. Similar discrepancies have been noted earlier. For instance, Morris¹¹ calculated the Lattice energy of CoBr_2 to be 536 and 624 Kcal/mole by two methods, but according to Yatsimirskii¹² it is 633. Similarly the values for CoI_2 and ZnI_2 are reported as 502, 605, 614 and 477, 576, 617 K.cal/mole respectively by the three methods. Such divergence may be marked¹³ in the Lattice energy values of co-ordination compounds like $\text{Fe}(\text{NH}_3)_6\cdot\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Mn}(\text{NH}_3)_6\cdot\text{Cl}_2$. For the former, the values are 395 and 423K .cal/mole by thermochemical cycle and electrostatic considerations and for the second, the values are 374 and 391 K.cal/mole respectively.

So, keeping in view the results of the present investigation and literature data it may be said that the values of Lattice energy may not be helpful to judge the stability of complexes. Moreover, in view of the uncertainty involved in evaluating the Lattice energy, the heat of formation cannot be found out with any fair degree of accuracy.

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11. D. F. C. Morris, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1957, 4, 8.
12. K. B. Yatsimirskii, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1958, 3, 2244.
13. *The Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds*, Edited by J. C. Bailar, Reinhold Publishing Corpn., New York, 1956, p. 143.